

IPBES Transformative Change Assessment Chapter 5. Data Management Report 5.4 Literature review on governance

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Description

This review corresponds to the IPBES transformative change assessment. The scoping report requests chapter 5 to provide a synthesis and assessment of instruments, including governance frameworks, that enable and encourage transformative change at all scales for a sustainable world. It is also in chapter 5 mandate to assess institutional design, emergence, evolution and operation of governance structures and processes for attending to the ongoing, dynamic and unpredictable nature of transformative change. A literature review encompassing multiple literature searches and strategies to identify relevant sources was conducted, and it is described in this report. Literature searches include specific searches for planning and reporting processes to the Convention on Biological Diversity and its national implementation. Further searches also focused on knowledge generation and informed governance, social experimentation and learning, coordination and inclusive governance, integrated and adaptive governance, as well as governance practices including institutional entrepreneurship, corruption and criminal activities in general.

Process Overview

Protocol

1. Literature review of the Convention on Biological Diversity and of the National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs)

Type of analysis/search/review: Academic literature review

Exact date of search: Between September 2022 and April 2023

Language: English

Search terms, search engine and sample extracted:

Search terms	Search engine	Sample extracted (records)
"National report*" AND "Convention on biological diversity" AND "review mechanism*" period of publication 2011-2023	Google Scholar	37
ALL=(NBSAP) OR ALL=("Biodiversity Strategies") OR ALL=("Biodiversity Policy Integration") OR ALL=("Biodiversity Mainstreaming")	Web of Science	73
"Monitoring and evaluation of policies, programmes and projects; Biodiversity; Social movements or activism and social change" OR "Monitoring and evaluation of policies, programmes and projects; Biodiversity; civil society; inclusive or inclusion" OR "Monitoring and evaluation of policies, programmes and projects; Biodiversity; civil society; adaptive or adaptation" OR "Monitoring and evaluation of policies, programmes and projects; Biodiversity; civil society; reflexive governance"	Complementary Index, Environment complete, MEDLINE, Science Direct, EBSCO	22

Treatment applied: Based on expert knowledge, screening of titles, abstracts and keywords were analyzed to identify whether documents were relevant for the topic. A total of 65 articles were selected, available and thus read thoroughly. A total of 10 was discarded because considered irrelevant of the scope of chapter 5. Additionally, 3 papers were added which were already known by the researchers and didn't come up in the research. In the end, 58 papers were used for a structured analysis, where experts were looking to understand if the processes and policies envisioned and induced by CBD and NBSAPs provide the institutional conditions for transformative governance (i.e., inclusive, informed, adaptive, integrated, and accountable).

Location and format of the data (A): IPBES_TCA_DMR5.4_CDB and NBSAPs literature review_(A).csv

2. Informed governance and research implementation gaps

Type of analysis/search/review: Academic literature review

Search engine: Google Scholar

Exact date of search: November 2023

Language: English

Search terms and sample extracted:

Search terms	Sample extracted (records)
"biodiversity" AND "informed governance" AND "integrated assessment"	13
"Research-implementation gap"	4

Treatment applied: Based on expert knowledge, screening of titles, abstracts and keywords were analyzed to identify whether documents were relevant for the topic. Articles were thoroughly read and used throughout chapter 5. One additional relevant paper was added to the results.

Location and format of the data (B): IPBES_TCA_DMR5.4_implementation gaps_(B).csv

3. Abstract-based additional literature review on inclusive, collaborative, and adaptative governance and its impact on biodiversity

Type of analysis/search/review: Academic literature review

Search engine: Google Scholar and Web of Science

Exact date of search: Between September 2022 and April 2023

Language: English

Search terms and sample extracted:

Search terms	Sample extracted (records)
((AB=(inclusive) OR AB=(collaborative)) AND (AB=(governance) AND AB=(biodiversity)) AND (AB=(governance AND biodiversity)) AND AB=(transformative change))	5
((AB=(global governance)) AND AB=("compliance")) AND AB=(biodiversity)	8
((AB=(united nations)) AND AB=("compliance")) AND AB=(biodiversity)	8
AB=("integrative governance")	19
(TI=("biodiversity") OR TI=("biological diversity") OR TI=("nature")) AND (TI=("policy integration") OR TI=("policy coherence") OR TI=("mainstreaming"))	56

(AB=("adaptive governance") OR AB=(reflexive governance)) AND (AB=(biodiversity) OR AB=(nature) OR AB=(Biological diversity))	132
AB=("institutional entrepreneurship")	275
ALL=("accountability") AND ALL=(biodiversity)	253
AB=("corruption") AND (AB=("biodiversity") OR AB=("biological diversity") OR AB=("nature"))	
AB=("crime") AND (AB=("biodiversity") OR AB=("biological diversity") OR AB=("nature"))	1869
(((((TI=(decision making)) OR TI=(power)) OR TI=(extractivism)) OR TI=(elitism)) OR TI=(elite)) AND TI=(biodiversity)	88

Treatment applied: Based on expert knowledge, screening of titles, abstracts and keywords were analyzed to identify whether documents were relevant for the topic. Articles were screened for factors determining outcomes for nature and biodiversity used to form the evidence used throughout chapter 5.

Definitions of files

ID	Names	File Type	Size	Description
A	1_IPBES_TCA_DMR5.4_CDB and NBSAPs literature review_(A).csv	csv	14 KB	58 papers on CBD and NBSAPs analyzed by assessment experts
B	2_IPBES_TCA_DMR5.4_implementation gaps_(B).csv	csv	6 KB	18 papers on governance and research implementation gaps